

DL-nor-leucine (0.45) from L-leucine (0.73) in n-butanol : acetic acid (1 : 1) ; (iii) separation of DL-serine (0.30) from L-proline (0.64), DOPA (0.26) from DL-valine (0.83) and DL-iso-leucine (0.55) from DL-nor-leucine (0.83) in n-butanol : acetic acid : water (5 : 4 : 1) as binary separations. Other separations achieved are L-cysteine (0.07) from DL-alanine (0.26) and glycine (0.40), L-arginine (0.12) from DL-alanine (0.26) and L-leucine (0.60) and DOPA (0.30) and DL-valine (0.48) in n-butanol saturated with water and separation of DL-serine (0.30) from L-lysine (0.50) and DL-tryptophan (0.67) and L-ornithine (0.31) from DL-valine (0.55) and DL-iso-leucine (0.76) in n-butanol : acetic acid : water (5 : 3 : 2) as ternary separations.

Results and Discussion

The results of chromatographic studies indicate that in aqueous and mixed developing systems amino acids show considerable movement while most of the nonpolar systems failed to effect the movement due to insolubility or low solubility of amino acids in these systems. The adsorption of amino acids by paper, however small, may also be one of the factors and can not be ignored completely³. It is observed that on bismuth oxide paper spots of amino acids are sharp, compact and distinct with no or reduced tailings, which are commonly observed with unimpregnated paper. Further the mixed systems increase the resolving power⁴ and R_f values decrease considerably in comparison of unimpregnated paper. Thus the superiority of the impregnated paper over plain paper is due to high resolving capability and compactness of the spots⁵. It is also observed that in most of the systems R_f values increase with the length of side-chain, i.e. molecular weight of amino acids. Thus the R_f values follow the sequence : leucine > valine > alanine > glycine.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron(II) by Extraction of its Cyclohexylthioglycolate Complex with Chloroform

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IRON has been determined spectrophotometrically using some reagents¹. A new method is developed which is simple and sensitive and equally accurate

and may be applied for the determination of iron in certain alloys.

Experimental

Iron(II) solution was prepared by dissolving ammonium ferrous sulphate in dilute sulphuric acid and standardised by known methods². Cyclohexylthioglycolate was prepared by the reported method³. A 0.1% solution of the cyclohexylthioglycolate was prepared in ethanol. Buffer solution of ammonia/ammonium acetate was used to adjust the pH.

Procedure : To an aliquot of sample solution containing 2.18–44.8 μg iron, was added 0.1% cyclohexylthioglycolate (1.5 ml), ammonia buffer (2.0 ml), potassium nitrate solution (1 ml) and chloroform (10 ml). The mixture was shaken gently for 1 min and allowed to settle when two phases separated immediately. The chloroform layer containing the extracted complex was poured on to the anhydrous sodium sulphate (2 g) to remove the last traces of water. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 520 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of cyclohexylthioglycolate and iron-cyclohexylthioglycolate in chloroform solutions were measured against ethanol and reagents blank respectively.

Extraction of iron-cyclohexylthioglycolate was carried out at different pH values from which the optimum pH range was found to be 8.5–9.2. The extractions were quantitative with 1.0–2.0 ml of the 0.1% reagent solution. In all the cases, 1.5 ml of the reagent was used. It was observed that the absorption remained constant upto 30 ml of the aqueous phase and above this the extraction was not quantitative.

Effects of various electrolytes such as sodium chloride, sodium acetate, potassium chloride and potassium nitrate (0.02–0.6 M) were studied. The extraction was found to be quantitative if the electrolyte concentration was not less than 0.05 M. So 0.1 M potassium nitrate was used in each case.

No change was observed in the extent of extraction when shaking time was varied from 30 s to 2 min; 1 min of shaking was enough for the quantitative extraction of the complex into chloroform.

The composition of iron-cyclohexylthioglycolate was established by Job's method of continuous variation and the mole-ratio method. A sharp peak at 0.67 mole fraction of ligand in Job's curve and a clear break at 1 : 2 metal-cyclohexylthioglycolate ratio in mole-ratio plot suggest the formation of 1 : 2 complex under these conditions.

Calibration curve : With the optimum conditions described above, a calibration curve was constructed for iron-cyclohexylthioglycolate at 520 nm. Beer's law was found to be obeyed over the concentration

range 2.18–44.8 μg in 10 ml of the final solution. The solution containing 22.4 μg of iron gave a mean absorbance of 0.280 when measured in a 1 cm cell with a relative standard deviation of 0.71%. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were calculated to be $0.70 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.008 \mu\text{g Fe/cm}^2$ respectively.

Interference: The interference of various ions was studied. Generally, 10 mg of alkali and 1 mg of metal ion were added individually to iron solution. Among the anions examined, only fluoride and EDTA interfered. Among the metal ions studied, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} interfered. Cobalt was masked by adding 5% sodium cyanide, while nickel complex was broken by heating with 2M HCl and the interference due to palladium was removed by extracting the palladium-cyclohexylthioglycolate complex at low pH (pH 4.5).

Analysis of alloys: A solution of the alloy (50–100 mg) was prepared in aqua regia. An aliquot was taken, treated with 10% hydroxylamine hydrochloride (4 ml) and extracted by the given procedure. Cobalt was masked with 5 ml of 5% sodium cyanide and nickel complex was broken by heating with 2M HCl. The interference due to palladium was removed by pre-extracting at pH 4.5 and the iron content was determined by the given procedure. Five determinations were made for each alloy and the results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF IRON IN ALLOYS

Alloy	Certified composition of the alloy %	Amount of iron taken μg	Amount of iron found μg	Average μg	Relative standard deviation %
Steel 33rd (NBS)	Fe, 90.3 ; Ni, 2.38 ;	18.06	18.00	18.02	0.22
	Cr, 0.32 ;		18.06		
	C, 2–3 ;		18.08		
	Mn, 0.68 ;		18.00		
	Si, 1.63 ;		18.00		
	Cu, 1.54		18.00		
Stainless steel no. 306	Fe, 70–70 ;	28.00	28.2	28.14	0.47
	Cr, 16.5 ;		28.3		
	Ni, 12.0 ;		28.0		
	Mo, 2–3		28.0		

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Cyclopentane-spiro-2'-(1-phenyl-2',4'-dithio)-s-triazine as a Chromogenic Reagent for Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper(II)†

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LITERATURE reports the use of thiotriazines as chromogenic reagents for the determination of copper(II)^{1,2}. The present work describes a simple method for the extraction spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) using cyclopentane-spiro-2'-(1-phenyl-2',4'-dithio)-s-triazine (CPSPDTT) as the reagent.

Experimental

CPSPDTT was prepared according to the described method³ and was recrystallised from ethanol to get analytically pure compound, m.p. 186–87°, mol. wt. 277. The reagent was found to be stable at room temperature at least for two months. A 0.002 M solution of CPSPDTT in dimethyl formamide was used. Standard stock solution of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R.) and was standardised⁴. A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic spectrophotometer was used for all spectral determinations. pH-measurements were made using Control Dynamics digital pH meter (C.D. Instruments).

To an aliquot of the solution containing 5–50 μg of copper(II) was added phosphate buffer (5 ml) of pH 7.0, followed by dilution with distilled water to 25 ml. To the mixture was added 0.002 M CPSPDTT (2 ml) in DMF followed by the addition of toluene (10 ml). After equilibration for 30 s the toluene layer was separated, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance measured at 410 nm against toluene as reference.

Results and Discussion

Toluene extract of the copper complex showed maximum and steady absorbance over the pH range 5.5–12.5. All other examinations were carried out at pH 7.0 using phosphate buffer as it was found suitable. From various solvents studied toluene was found to be most suitable for extraction of the complex.

Intense yellow coloured extracted complex exhibited maximum absorbance at 410 nm. At similar conditions, the reagent blank practically did not absorb above 390 nm. Reagent concentration study showed that 2 ml of 0.002 M CPSPDTT was sufficient to extract 40 μg of copper(II) in a single

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